

Research Article

New Investigations and Findings in the Pathophysiology, Psychopathology, Pharmacotherapy, and Psychotherapy of Psychopathy

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How to cite this article: M. Victor, M. Cedric, C. Vargas, M. Caixeta. (2025). New Investigations and Findings in the Pathophysiology, Psychopathology, Pharmacotherapy, and Psychotherapy of Psychopathy, International Journal of Psychiatric Practice, RPC Publishers, 2(2); DOI: <https://www.doi.org/rpc/2025/rpc.ijpp/00406>

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Submitted: August 10, 2025

Approved: September 05, 2025

Published: September 11, 2025

Abstract

Psychopathy has traditionally been conceptualized as an affective deficit, centered on coldness, lack of empathy, and insensitivity to others. However, clinical experience suggests that this model is insufficient. Many individuals who meet diagnostic criteria for antisocial personality disorder are described by relatives and physicians as affectionate, caring, and emotionally expressive. This article proposes a new paradigm for understanding psychopathy, emphasizing difficulties in temporal self-projection, deficits in working memory, and dysfunctions in mirror neurons. Based on more than 45 years of psychiatric practice, we argue that psychopathy is not limited to emotional coldness but is deeply related to failures in futurization, self-referential thinking, and symbolic paternal structuring. Therapeutic strategies, including pharmacological stabilization of mood and impulsivity and psychotherapeutic interventions oriented toward temporal integration, are discussed.

Keywords: psychopathy; coldness; mirror neurons; working memory; futurization; psychotherapy; pharmacotherapy

Introduction

The dominant paradigm in psychiatry has described psychopathy as an affective deficit marked by emotional coldness, lack of empathy, and insensitivity toward others (Hare, 1999; Blair, 2005). While these features are indeed present in many cases, clinical experience reveals contradictions: individuals with psychopathic behaviours are sometimes reported as affectionate, caring, and emotionally generous. This paradox challenges the assumption that coldness is the core element of psychopathy. The present article develops an alternative model of psychopathy, rooted in failures of temporal integration and self-referential cognition, linked to working memory deficits and mirror neuron dysfunction.

Methods

This study is based on 45 years of continuous clinical psychiatric practice in outpatient, inpatient, and forensic settings, including longitudinal observation of patients diagnosed with antisocial personality disorder and related conditions. Clinical vignettes and therapeutic interventions were analysed phenomenologically and psychodynamically, integrating neurobiological and developmental perspectives.

Results

Temporal Dimension of Psychopathy

Psychopaths struggle to project themselves into the future. Whereas neurotypical individuals can use past experiences to anticipate future emotional consequences, individuals with psychopathy often remain bound to immediate impulses, such as sexual desire or aggression. This failure of “futurization” leads to poor decision-making and disregard for long-term attachments (Damasio, 1994).

Mirror Neuron Dysfunction and Self-Reference

Deficits in mirror neuron functioning impair both the perception of others’ states and the capacity to reflect upon oneself [Gallese, 2003]. As a result, psychopathic individuals are unable to “see themselves,” preventing critical self-reflection and the construction of moral responsibility.

Role of Family and Symbolic Castration

The absence of paternal function—understood as the transmission of love, discipline, obligation, and symbolic castration—aggravates psychopathic tendencies. Without such structuring, the individual remains impulsive, functioning serially rather than in parallel, unable to block instincts through reflective self-control [Lacan, 1977].

Pharmacological and Psychotherapeutic Interventions

Although traditionally considered untreatable, psychopathy can benefit from a combined therapeutic approach. Mood stabilizers such as lithium, valproate, and carbamazepine may improve emotional regulation [Goodwin & Jamison, 2007]. Antipsychotics such as haloperidol can reduce impulsivity and aggression, promoting ataraxia and greater compliance with social rules (Arnt & Skarsfeldt, 1998). Psychotherapy focused on temporal integration, moral reasoning, and relational capacity may complement pharmacological strategies.

Discussion

This reinterpretation moves beyond the reductionist model of psychopathy as mere coldness. While deficits of affectivity are evident, they are neither the sole nor the primary pathological element. Instead, failures in working memory, futurization, and mirror neuron functioning provide a more comprehensive framework. Furthermore, our clinical data suggest that most psychopathic individuals are hyperactive subjects with poor family environments, consistent with evidence linking childhood adversity, ADHD traits, and antisocial outcomes [Farrington, 2005; Matthys et al., 2013]. Thus, psychopathy must be understood as a multidimensional disorder involving biological, psychological, and social determinants. The new paradigm proposed here opens avenues for treatment and challenges the dogma of psychopathy as incurable.

A New Interpretation of Psychopathic Coldness

What draws our clinical attention, initially, is that although some patients exhibit psychopathic behaviours that is, they meet criteria for antisocial personality disorder, such as repeated fights, crimes, drug use, emotional instability, putting their own interests above others, harming, hurting, despising, or abandoning others—it is common to hear from physicians or families that “the patient is actually very affectionate, very caring, he gives away his belongings, he shares his food, and he is, in fact, very affectionate.” This does not align well with the hypothesis that the psychopathic problem is purely affective coldness. The problem can also be understood from another dimension.

The Temporal Dimension of Psychopathy

Consider, for example, a psychopathic behaviour: a married man with children meets an attractive, seductive woman and wants to abandon his family to be with her. If he projects himself into the future and imagines being without his family, his children, and his wife’s love, he might reconsider. This future-oriented feeling could help him counter his present impulse. At the present moment, he may be conflicted between family love and sexuality. Sexuality often prevails because it is more material, stronger, and immediate. However, when projecting himself into the future—using the past lived with his family as material for this projection—he may realize that he prefers his family. Then, feelings of preference, inner peace, gratitude, comfort, happiness, and calmness arise, combating the raw sexual impulse. Psychopaths, however, have difficulty projecting themselves into the future. They struggle to see themselves, to reflect on their own thoughts and conduct. This is related to working memory deficits. They cannot think in parallel, only in serial form. They move only forward, unable to step back and reconsider. They cannot think about their own thinking or conduct. This difficulty is linked to dysfunctions in the mirror neuron system. Psychopaths show a certain insensitivity to themselves, an inability to perceive their own sensations. As a result, they do not regulate themselves well, do not observe themselves clearly, and do not critically reflect on their actions.

Mirror Neuron Dysfunction and Lack of Self-Reference

Just as they have difficulty perceiving what comes from others—sometimes appearing inept, somewhat Asperger-like, socially awkward, or emotionally cold—they also lack the ability to perceive what comes from within. They cannot stop and look at themselves, and this self-reflection is crucial for thinking about the future. The future is essentially a projection of the self ahead, built upon past experiences. Psychopaths fail to perform this complex mental engineering. They live only in the present, in a serial, linear flow.

Therapeutic Implications

From a therapeutic point of view, an adequate family may help mitigate these biological deficits by instilling moral principles and constantly teaching about the future and universal laws – such as the law of love, attraction, interaction, mutual aid, altruism, charity, complexity, evolution, stability, and perseverance. Some individuals, despite having hyperactive traits and mirror neuron dysfunctions, possess a stronger “soul,” meaning a deeper connection with universal

principles. This inner connection allows them to overcome, to some extent, their neurobiological deficiencies, synchronizing with universal laws and thus being able to regulate their own body and mind. The absence of adequate symbolic castration in childhood, usually transmitted by a father who provides love, discipline, law, duty, and occupation, also contributes to psychopathy. Without this structuring, the individual does not learn to stop, to block impulses, and to reflect on themselves. They remain serial rather than parallel, impulsively moving forward.

Biological and Pharmacological Perspectives

Although it is often said that “psychopaths cannot be cured” and that reclusion is the only solution – which is indeed very difficult-some interventions can help.

- Mood regulation: lithium, valproate, carbamazepine.
- Hyperactivity treatment: since many so-called psychopaths are hyperactive.
- Impulsivity and aggression control: antipsychotics such as haloperidol, which calm the patient, provide ataraxia, increase compliance, and improve acceptance of rules.
- Thus, we can act biologically, cognitively, and psychotherapeutically.

Rethinking Coldness in Psychopathy

Psychopaths are indeed “cold” in the sense that they feel less of what others feel, but this coldness is not always the central element of psychopathy. Often, the problem lies in deficits of theory of mind and futurization. Clinically, many psychopaths are affectionate, able to feel visceral and primitive emotions. What they lack is not the capacity to feel emotions but the capacity to integrate them into long-term moral choices. In our 45 years of psychiatric experience, about 90% of psychopathic patients correspond to hyperactive individuals with poor family backgrounds. Hyperactivity is itself associated with deficits in working memory, learning difficulties, novelty seeking, and dopamine dependence. Without concern for others, they become self-centred, instinct-driven, and detached from their environment – another consequence of mirror neuron dysfunction. Thus, psychopathy involves much more than emotional coldness. While they indeed feel emotions less intensely than others, this is not the only nor the main pathophysiological element. Psychopathy must be understood as a multidimensional disorder, integrating biological, cognitive, and environmental factors.

Conclusion

Psychopathy is not solely defined by emotional coldness. It involves profound impairments in temporal self-projection, reflective cognition, and relational structuring. These impairments are linked to deficits in working memory and mirror neuron functioning, often exacerbated by dysfunctional family environments. A therapeutic approach integrating pharmacological stabilization and psychotherapeutic strategies focused on futurization may provide new hope for patients traditionally deemed untreatable.

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